

IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE MUSIC CULTURE - PEOPLE, THE ROLE OF THE SONG

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Abstract. This article folk song express the opinions that have become the cultural and spiritual heritage of the performing arts, we have not, and they were reworked by Uzbek composers, the style and the instrument, the factor that elevate the spiritual world of the young generation.

Keywords, acapella, mode, monody, harmony, texture, polyphony, canon, antiphon, imitation, melis by mordent, grace note, conductor, choirmaster.

Music - a training tool which has an impressive huge power, the power of living as human spiritual beraoladigan can ozug'idir. The almighty has the power to charm with its music, which cover the human soul. The beauty of the soul music who are eager only meant that he loves. Listening to music and was trained from childhood to the perception of it, and are by nature, have been trained. Further development of the sense of human beauty, such a stand, perfect for a spiritual disorder will not be talked about. The formation and nurturing of these subtle emotions of music is one of the powerful tools. Music is the type of art importance of art and education. The spiritual perfection of man the delivery of the art of music is incomparable. Sounds of music which is not executed by the representative of the people or nations, most noble, high and thin is an expression

of human experiences. Over progressing for thousands of years people found the form of music, of each nation have become rich cultural and spiritual badiylashib raised high bounce. The music, the lifestyle of the people of the people of uzbekistan, ethics-ethics or religion at some aspects of hugs, dreams and hopes, to work, love of the motherland, will tarannum your commitment to love. People, holidays, holidays, large gatherings, weddings-one can only imagine the movement of the music without distraction. I am playing them in every sing-song, dance of the participants of the results showed a positive effect on the mental. The ceremony was performed in holiday and festival, people to the landscape created by the nature of the song, the relationship came into being as a result of social realities. The people of uzbekistan the nature of the music, society, and human behavior, the perception of the beautiful events bilateral relations, and serves them to enjoy. Certain conditions arising in all people of the song reflects life. The music man to the mind of people the most impressive works of art as a tool tevarak-will help to soak it in and the events that took place around the events. People always has attracted the creation of the songs and music. Each of the processing works from the composer requires a careful study of folk song.

The tones of the song and performing arts people we have in - processing sector is a certain genre of music, creativity and professional bastakorlik kompozitorlik. Many voice music song in the land of the controversy, garmoniyalashga, partial close, but the style is somewhat complex. If the processing of schools is important in the formation of the nation kompozitorlik tones, which performs the function of the initial stage, after all, assisting in the development of the national musical style of the creative function. Most hojibekov from u., Z. Paliashvili, M. Dzhizak, E. grid, take n. lisenko, B. Barton, J. Gershvin, S. Pro-kofyev, L. Yanacheklarni example I can show you. The music of the past and variability of uzbekistan the creativity of the performer, like an oral factor-based, then the option of creating a wide range of musical tunes and classical singing or the way people starring. This

tradition of creativity bastakorlik structural turned to the direction, when All T. Y. Rajabiy he said that artists and other people's tones were created in the ground of processing monodiya mature samples.

We have a large performing arts take place in the processing of the tones of people in uzbekistan's musical drama, opera, ballet, music simfonik, australia, oratoriya, kamer music of the genre is an important factor in the development of the master plan. Initial experience in this field, the end of xix century – the beginning of the xx century klenovskiy n., F. Ley, N. Mironov, K. Abdullaev, 3. In the works of other composers create music and maqsudov singdirishaolmadi Uzbek heritage properties. 1920 - V. Uspenskiy people like other composers of the songs in 30 years, for example "Zarkokil", "chaman flowers" are like, "farhad and shirin" and the musical singing in the status of dramasi complex ways, for example "Stem", "Chorgoh" garmoniya limited opportunities in the audience as I have used many tools for processing voice, especially without music. Only half of 1930 ikkichi A. Kozlovskiy four farg'onacha "Tanavor", "far from the kyrgyz", "Fig'on" and "Flower face", the band simfonik for processing voice and singing, music voice of many tools has wide application, especially, "Tanavor" at prominent artistic results. Feel mush G. 1941. "55 of uzbekistan in the people's song" the collection was created. Many music traditions monodiya voice and an integral link in them. In recent years, based on folk tunes Ik chorus accompaniment. Akbarov, S., boboev b. Umidjonovlar has been in the development of creativity. B. the estate, T. Sodiqov, B. Giyenko, M. Leviyev, D. Zokirov, s. and most other people's tunes to a variety of loss of galilee, that is, alone together, alone and together, fortepiano, were processed for ensembles and orchestras.

Especially when working with this process, which is a natural voice will be with the people's songs show an extremely thin. Ko'povozli the formation and development of national music, the song he is one of the people in that place.

Great, the most outstanding song of the fraternal peoples of uzbekistan mutavakkil burhanov re-gloss, giving adapted for most first team performance. Her mature artistic level processed at the people of uzbekistan songs: “my sweetheart” or “Tanovar”, “beautiful girl” or “ganj karabakh”, karakalpak folk song “Bibigul”, uyghur folk song “Sayram”, the people of tajikistan's song “flower particles” and “Towards tall ko'hi” still works as accompaniment-chorus and the creation of art to serve as a model for the composers still is being executed. The music of the chorus of these works has become the benchmark model-specific. Sobir by talented boboev his followers, and a number of Hardy Umidjonov xormeysterlar Sh.Yormatov, J. Shukurov, it doubles.Nechayev, N. Sharafiyevalar the chorus of the song adapted for people dissimilar results obtained. Processing - independent sector of creativity and interesting people each song unique culture, to show the specific characteristics of, and able to reveal his musical thinking. The main task of processing through different means specific obrazlilik ifodaviy the content of the song, its national “color paint”, giving you the option to open it. S. boboev chorus performer for the re-worked “Chaman ichra”, “Yali-yali”, “Time”, “Tanovar”, “senday Now” people are also educational and professional chorus of songs at present in the program has been sounded. In this regard, especially the master conductor, xormeyster creative uzbekistan connoisseur of the art of the chorus, the song umidjonovning most hardy of hundreds of people is re-used, new, create original works of art in the chorus of people enjoy our services is much larger. It “Ilillayor”, “Qorasoch”, “Chamandagul”, “Qilpillama”, “Lap”, “Galbari” the uzbekistan people's songs, folk song from central asia and various “heart” I am the people of tajikistan's song, “Yapuray” Kazakh folk song), “well-known play”, “who fertilized the mek's”, “Almixan” uyghur folk song, “Qomuzchu”, “Chaloyna as” not only the creation of the miniature, as well as the traditional classic professional music samples to be adapted to the status of b. umidjonovning ko'povozli also the

contribution of the chorus is great. Processed by his “Segoh” g'azal will Xurshid, “Chorgoh” g'azal will Furkat, “Saraxbori Today” with new paint and a rasp in his performance will g'azal chorus sounded. Chorus accompaniment for the master conductor of the pamir people based on the song “Dilbarume”, tatar folk song is based on “the ulom yash” and “the light of happiness” syuitalarini also created. B. academic activity in the process of the way Umidjonov xormeysterlik chorus performer - performing coordination with national traditions commanded. Uzbekistan national chorus performer find the specific style and trim, as well as people's artist of Uzbekistan, the great chorus conductor, and composer Umidjonovning work and professionalism Was incomparable. This is distinct from the chorus of the execution-style on his national team to the other team. Chorus master of all of the works adapted for radio and tv shows, mainly to uzbekistan magnetic tape called the golden fund of the republic “in the chorus, showing the team service” many tunes, come enjoy our people. Chorus master professor with a successful business team showing the various DOUBLES. The people of uzbekistan nechayevning songs: “do'ppi Zar”, “Namanganning of apples”, “Ho laylo”, “Slits”, songs of the uyghur people “Nazugum”, “Dutarimning tarliri”, “Chiraylig'im”, “Seriq sebde”, the Turkmen people's song “Bibijan”, songs of the people of tajikistan “the spring of the ink-tu”, “mezanad Presence jonon”, Kazakh folk song from “qasida Aytim salemqalam”, karakalpak folk song “from ceylon kiz”, who is still functioning today Sharafiyevaning professor n. “melodies of uzbekistan”, “Ey nozanin”, “margin Architecture”, “the garden of travel”, “Humor”, “O mexribonim”, “Tasadduq”, “Mustahzod”, “the blessings of nowruz”, “-Says either”, tatar folk song from “Recognize when atga”, karakalpak folk song from “I have to laugh as the number like” also can bring a number of works. Teachers song, genre, tone, content, content depending on the characteristics of the tone of the chorus, a variety of writing-those who use the technique district. A voice from the song-world european type ko'povozli

tarannum polifonik sound under a wide range of influences and a form aspect and access to the content of faktura-have managed to rise. People of the song, i.e. in the process of processing for performing the chorus of the song have mono ko'povozlilikning follow the principle of dynamic growth of the pace, unless we are in a relatively simple form, which is ko'povozlilik style chorus quart-kvinta interval, paralel we can see the movement of the voices. Especially the chorus part of this action, the musical accompaniment, which will assume the balanced complete background image is used in cases. Such musical performer performer belonging style "dutar" two voice belongs to. Antifon people in the process of the songs, i.e. dialog, the canyon, the way you use too much of imitation-because of their music, the national niladi nature, its various see bright showing to give the shape of typical imaging monodiyasi of him opened within the framework of uzbekistan with the opportunity to enrich berishva ko'povozlilik paint creates. Ko'povozlilikning extend along the shape of the other style, we have the songs polifonik method in the process of being justified by the benefits from the people to the people the most professional and too simple to xormeysterlar to become engaged in the processing of the songs. One of the sources of the songs people the complexity of the processing method. Especially, the method of the republic of rhythmic music-ifodaviy is incomparable features. The rhythm method is also different to most of our skillfully adapted ko'povozlilikka a rich framework of the tattoo, colorful special effects that we see. Many more people adapted the song ko'povozlikka koloristik effects - yumiq voice sounds floured vokallashtirish, the special unit from a combination of "bum-bak", "ra-na-na", "cancer-tak-tak", "yor-yor", "yoroney" applause to playing, fingers qirsillatish various further enhances and enriches the development of music xayqirishlardan the use of the song. Melizmlar, forshlag, decorate them more jozibaliroq mordentlar more tones, nafisroq, ensures you will be more beautiful. This artistic creation of the songs of the Uzbek people and has the main musical direction for the execution of the song

without retaining adapted consider the volume of the chorus. In the song, the meaning of the text depending on the direction of the group of the basic tone, sometimes men, sometimes women in the series, given to the group. Worth mentioning that, in music, the folklore of every nation is unique, this will also appear xalqqagina only specific features. For processing, strict conditions are not met when the national mandatory without change, that is, keep the rhythm and melody of the tone with the details of the specific. As it is known, is the start of the era of aesthetic emotions bringing up the young man. National pride, national feeling and national values, loyalty to tradition, the mother respect to the ground - all of these impregnated starting from the period of his youth to man. Also based on folk songs were among the most important tasks of nurturing the children. In this regard, the conductor, people's artist of uzbekistan, the most Sh.Children's chorus of the children's folk song adapted for very many of yormatov it should be emphasized is the transition of the game. "Boychechak", "Chittigul", "lola" as, "This word gulshan", "jamalak gold," a number of children people as the composer of the song is based on several years of experience in the case of children, adapted for chorus. Team performance in the educational significance of this song, further strengthening effective. So, human life through the true beauty of people use music as a spiritual aesthetic effects ko'rsatishkishida the ability to enjoy content from people to do creative work in the way of happiness, will help you to realize aspirations, to become a spiritual man perfect. Sing-song a man's man as a social creature dwelling the main formation and the mental-spiritual factor. Every type of man in the spiritual nurturing of the song people performs a specific function. People of the song, or children, or older in age community chorus-all men of the world, the popularity of further they sing together, awakened consciousness of affection for one another closer to motivate the development of feelings. People ko'povozlilik respect to the idea of goodness in the execution of the content of the song, mexr-effects, their history, culture,

boasting a pure conscience, honest work, good human qualities such as being faithful, it was expressed the essence of. Chorus art also human and spiritual levels, the increase of artistic taste-ha, and human advancement aesthetic pleasure in them united is one of the types of art that can evoke. This art of healthy young generation of the youth, spiritual, artistic and ethical culture the formation of national pride, patriotism, education, the implementation of elegance and creativity, the world views the expansion of bilateral relations serves to grow independence and initiative.

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